
25. The origin of Oumuamua

THE MENTAL PICTURE of our solar system that I had in my mind as a young boy was, of course, absurdly simplistic. Nine planets orbited our Sun. Some were big and gaseous or icy, others were rocky, some were surrounded by moons, and there was also a ring of asteroids and the occasional comet.

Half a century on, my view is very different. I see it as magnificent in its scale, in its architecture, and in its beauty. I see it as bewilderingly and endlessly complex, rich in its complex chemistry, pervaded by a startling variety of remarkable physical phenomena, and whose origin and formation we are only just beginning to comprehend. Everywhere we look, and the closer we look, it seems ever more bizarre, ever more complex, ever more finely balanced, and ever more mysterious.

Major advances in our knowledge have been gained only rather recently: for example, the energy source of the Sun was understood, as nuclear fusion, only in 1927. The vast complexity of the planets and their satellites has been won through deep space missions, observing them with flybys, orbiters, and landers.

And the seeming infinity of its smaller bodies and their complex motions – asteroids, near-Earth asteroids, Kuiper belt objects, trans-Neptunian objects, comets and their deep-space reservoir of the Oort Cloud – continue to surprise both observers and theoreticians.

THE DISCOVERY of the first planets beyond our solar system in the 1990s, and the remarkable advances in discovery numbers, their highly detailed observations, and supporting theories and numerical modelling, has transformed our understanding of the formation of planetary systems in general, and of our solar system in particular. From these multidisciplinary and concentrated efforts we now have a much better ‘big picture’ of its formation and subsequent evolution.

Four and a half billion years ago, gas and dust in the interstellar medium collapsed into a flattened rotating disk, our Sun forming at the centre, and the planets progressively growing out of the material in the disk as these assembled into ever bigger agglomerations. Closer to the Sun, where temperatures were higher, the rocky

planets and their satellites grew out of the less-volatile debris, their gravity competing for any residual material in their orbital dominions. Further out, where temperatures were much lower, the more volatile ices and gases gradually condensed and slowly swept up the vast remaining reservoirs of gas to form the outer giant planets.

Left over from the final assembly of the planets was a vast range of debris still circling the Sun: rocky asteroids closer to it, the small icy lumps of the Oort cloud comets far out in a vast spherical cloud.

Gravitational forces between the bigger bodies and the smaller debris particles acted as slingshots, propelling the latter (and sometimes the former) into perturbed and often unusual orbits. Some of these smaller bodies would have been hurled out at very high velocities, often high enough to escape the gravitational embrace of the host system.

IF THIS BROAD PICTURE is correct – and the enormous weight of today’s vast range of observational, theoretical, and modelling efforts make it compellingly so – one specific consequence seems inevitable.

Detailed models of the gravitational scattering that takes place during the later stages of planetary formation, in our solar system and in others, implies that interstellar space should have extrasolar planetesimals and comets passing through it, flung out as a by-product of the star-formation and planetary-formation process.

Some of these, from nearby stellar systems, will end up passing through our solar system. These *interstellar vagabonds* should be recognisable by their extreme hyperbolic orbits, contrasting with the elliptical (bound) orbits of the vast majority of solar system objects.

SERIOUS SEARCHES FOR SUCH objects started around 1990. The usual way of discovering objects in the solar system is from repeated deep imaging of some part of the sky, repeated days or weeks later to see if any objects might be moving. The changing position of a moving object can be measured repeatedly, and its orbit eventually determined and refined.

A handful of possible candidates, including the objects denoted C/2007 W1 and C/1853 E1 discovered around 2010–15, were later rejected on the basis of improved orbits which ruled out hyperbolic trajectories, and categorised them instead as bound to the solar system.

THEORETICAL WORK over the past 20–30 years has attempted to estimate the number of interstellar vagabonds that might be passing through our solar system today. Assuming that each star system ejects 10^{13} km-sized planetesimals, the local space density would be only one object in every 1000 cubic astronomical units. One might pass within 5 au of the Sun every year or so. So not only would they be extremely rare, but they would also be extremely difficult to spot: a 1-km size object at 5 au would be only ~ 24 mag. It is not surprising that none had been found.

Later estimates used improved models of debris disks, planetesimal scattering, expected size distributions, and assuming the low reflectivity of inactive comets, but with similar conclusions.

THE ASTRONOMY WORLD, and many beyond, were captivated by the announcement of a real such interstellar traveller in October 2017. Named Oumuamua, from the Hawaiian for ‘scout’, it was discovered with the wide-field survey instrument Pan-STARRS, some 40 days after its closest approach to the Sun.

Still within the orbit of Mercury, and very faint at only 22 mag, it was quickly confirmed as a minor body some 100 metres in size, on a hyperbolic orbit with a very high eccentricity (at $e = 1.192$, the highest known), and with an incoming velocity of around 26 km s^{-1} .

By the end of 2017, only three months after its discovery, more than 30 groups had studied its orbit, and its shape, rotation and surface properties.

One of the big surprises was its strongly elongated shape (estimated at 5:1, or even 10:1) deduced from photometric measurements. An explanation was quickly forthcoming: in its travel through interstellar space for perhaps a million years, and free from larger impactors, many high-velocity impacts from micron-sized interstellar dust grains, would be energetic enough to repeatedly dislodge splinters and sculpt its elongated shape.

Some speculated that it was an ‘alien’ source, and radio telescope observations provided upper limits to any transmitter power. Some even suggested a fly-by mission, to be launched within 5–10 yr, and to chase it down before its departure from the solar system.

THERE HAS been much speculation about the origin of this interstellar traveller. But the challenge in pinpointing its origin comes down to our limited knowledge of star positions and their space motions. Traveling through interstellar space at 26 km s^{-1} , it would take a million years to cross 25 parsecs. Throughout that time, all the stars in our solar neighbourhood are themselves moving, and it will have been further deflected by close star encounters on its journey.

Its origin can only be deduced by following its motion backwards in time, taking into account the overall gravitational potential of our Galaxy, and all the individual perturbations from stars it has passed along its way.

In one of the pre-Gaia data studies, Dybczyński & Królikowski (2018) started with 201 763 nearby stars, finding just 109 that Oumuamua would have sped by within 3.5 parsecs. Only seven had an encounter closer than 1 parsec, with most of these occurring over the past 50–100 000 years. The closest, HIP 3757, had a fly-by distance of only 0.04 parsec, and happened 118 000 years ago. It passed by the second closest, GJ 4274, within 0.4 parsec, a mere 23 000 years ago.

THESE ARE UNLIKELY to be the origin of Oumuamua, because the fly-bys occurred with large relative velocities, of around $50\text{--}100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, implying a similarly large ejection velocity. Searching further back in time, and examining more than 200 000 candidate stars, they found only four candidate progenitors. Their most promising, HIP 113020 (GJ 876), is known to host a four-planet system. The encounter occurred 790 000 years ago, with a relative velocity of just 3.9 km s^{-1} .

More detailed models along similar lines, but using the Gaia DR2 data, are discussed by Bailer-Jones et al. (2018). Their closest encounter, at 0.60 pc some 1 Myr ago, was with the same M-dwarf, HIP 3757, with a relative velocity of 24.7 km s^{-1} . They found a more distant encounter, at 1.6 pc and 3.8 Myr ago, but with a lower encounter velocity of 10.7 km s^{-1} , with the G5 dwarf HD 292249. They found only two other stars with encounter distances and velocities intermediate to these.

The origin of Oumuamua remains a mystery, but even more definitive studies will be possible with the Gaia DR3 data. And beyond!